

KINEMATICS OF A PARTICLE

Mansurov Mahkamadyakub Kunduzovich

"Andijan Machine Building Institute", Andijan, Republic of Uzbekistan

Tel. (+998) 979936212

https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6664224

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022
Accepted: 02nd June 2022
Online: 15th June 2022

KEY WORDS

positive directions, arrangement, elevators

ABSTRACT

In the following two figures a, b, for example, the problem of positioning the mobile robot will be described. If the robot starts to move from a known position, the odometer (encoder) can track its movement, due to an error of the odometer, after a period of exercise, the robot its position uncertainty will become large. In order to make the uncertainty of the position will not increase indefinitely, the robot must refer to their external environment for their positioning.

The position of particle (block) B as shown in Fig. 1 depends upon the position of Particle (Положение частицы (блока) B, как показано на рис. 1, зависит от положения частицы (блока) A.lock) A. The positive directions of the velocity y'A and the acceleration y''A of A downwards (in the direction of increasing yA).

Положительные направления скорости y'A и ускорения y''A элемента A вниз (в сторону увеличения yA). Also, the positive directions of y'B and y''B of block B are downwards as shown in Fig. 1. Кроме того, положительные направления y'B и y''B блока B направлены вниз, как показано на рис. 1.

Fig. 1 Arrangement of one fixed pulley connected to another movable one Или это уравнение можно переписать как:

$$y_A - L_1 + \pi r_1 + (y_B - L_1 - L_2) + \pi r_2 + (y_B - L_2) = C_1$$

$$y_A + 2 y_B = C_2$$

$$v_A + 2 v_B = 0$$

$$a_A + 2 a_B = 0$$

$$y_A + 2 y_B = C_2$$

(1)

The first and second time derivatives of Eq. (1) give:

$$\dot{y}_A + 2 \dot{y}_B = 0$$

$$v_A + 2 v_B = 0$$

$$\ddot{y}_A + 2 \ddot{y}_B = 0$$

$$a_A + 2 a_B = 0$$

$$y_A + 2 y_D = C_3$$

$$v_A + 2 v_D = 0$$

$$a_A + 2 a_D = 0$$

$$y_B + 2 y_C - y_D = C_4$$

$$v_B + 2 v_C - v_D = 0$$

$$a_A + 2 a_D = 0$$

Among the most common applicable examples for motion of connected particles are elevators. Simply, the main components of the elevator are Electric Motor, Cabin, Counter weight, Counter weight cables and Pulleys.

Среди наиболее распространенных применимых примеров движения связанных частиц — лифты. Проще говоря, основными компонентами лифта являются электродвигатель, кабина, противовес, тросы противовеса и шкивы.

Example: In the pulley configuration shown in Fig., block A has a downward velocity of 0.3 m/s. Determine the velocity of block B.

Пример: В конфигурации шкива, показанной на рис., блок А движется вниз со скоростью 0,3 м/с. Определить скорость блока В.

$$L = 3y_B + 2y_A + constants$$

$$0 = 3v_B + 2v_A$$

$$0 = 3v_B + 2(0.3)$$

$$v_B = -0.2 \text{ m/s}$$

This means that the value of velocity of block B is 0.2 m/s and upward (the negative sign means that the motion of block B in direction of decreasing the value of y_B).
 Пример: В сборе шкивы, показанной на рис., блок А движется вниз со скоростью 0,3 м/с. Определить скорость блока В.

Relative Motion of two particles

Relative Position (Translating Axes)

The absolute position of A is seen to be determined by the vector \underline{r}_A as follows: Видно, что абсолютное положение А определяется вектором \underline{r}_A следующим образом:

$$\underline{r}_A = \underline{r}_B + \underline{r}_{A/B}$$

(A/B means A with respect to B)

Or this equation may be rewritten as:

$$\underline{r}_{A/B} = \underline{r}_A - \underline{r}_B$$

If the moving system axes x_1-y_1 are chosen at point A as shown in Fig. , the relative motion for position is given as:

$$\underline{r}_B = \underline{r}_A + \underline{r}_{B/A}$$

Or this equation may be rewritten as:

$$\underline{r}_{B/A} = \underline{r}_B - \underline{r}_A$$

it is seen that

$$\underline{r}_{A/B} = -\underline{r}_{B/A}$$

Relative Velocity

We differentiate position Eq. once with respect to time to obtain velocities The absolute of velocity of A is seen to be determined by the vector \underline{v}_A as follows:

$$\underline{v}_A = \underline{v}_B + \underline{v}_{A/B}$$

(A/B means A with respect to B)

Or this equation may be rewritten as:

$$\underline{v}_{A/B} = \underline{v}_A - \underline{v}_B$$

If the moving system axes x1-y1 are chosen at point A as shown in Fig. , the relative motion for velocity is given as:

$$\underline{v}_B = \underline{v}_A + \underline{v}_{B/A}$$

Or this equation may be rewritten as:

$$\underline{v}_{B/A} = \underline{v}_B - \underline{v}_A$$

it is seen that

$$\underline{v}_{A/B} = -\underline{v}_{B/A}$$

Relative Acceleration

We differentiate velocity Eq. once with respect to time to obtain accelerations. The absolute of acceleration of A is seen to be determined by the vector \underline{a}_A as follows:

$$\underline{a}_A = \underline{a}_B + \underline{a}_{A/B}$$

(A/B means A with respect to B)

Or this equation may be rewritten as:

$$\underline{a}_{A/B} = \underline{a}_A - \underline{a}_B$$

If the moving system axes x_1-y_1 are chosen at point A as shown in Fig. , the relative motion for acceleration is given as:

$$\underline{a}_B = \underline{a}_A + \underline{a}_{B/A}$$

Or this equation may be rewritten as:

$$\underline{a}_{B/A} = \underline{a}_B - \underline{a}_A$$

it is seen that

$$\underline{a}_{A/B} = -\underline{a}_{B/A}$$

References:

1. Anderson, M.G., Katz, P.B., 1998. Strategic sourcing. *International Journal of Logistics Management* 9 (1), 1-13.
2. Armistead, C.G., Mapes, J., 1993. The impact of supply chain integration on operating performance. *Logistics Information Management* 6 (4), 9-14.
3. Armstrong, A., Hagel III, J., 1996. The real value of online communities. *Harvard Business Review* (May/June), 134-140.
4. Baatz, E.B., 1995. CIO 100} Best practices: the chain gang. *CIO* 8 (19), 46-52.
5. Bechtel, C., and Jayaram, J.: *Supply Chain Management: A Strategic Perspective*. *International Journal of Logistics Management* 8(1), 15-34 (1997).
6. Birou, L.M., Fawcett, S.E., Magnan, G.M., 1998. The product life cycle: a tool for functional strategic alignment. *International Journal of Purchasing and Materials Management* 34 (2), 37-51.
7. Botta-Genoulaz, V., Gruat-La-Forme, F. A., Millet, P. A., Seville, M., Boucher, X., Derrouiche, R., Llerena, D., Neubert, G., Pellegrin, C., (2005) Questionnaire d'enquête sur les pratiques de partage d'informations par une entreprise participant à une chaîne logistique établie. *Projet COPILOTES, Région Rhône-Alpes*,